

were collected 7, 10, and 15 days after inoculation (DI). Leaves from uninoculated seedlings served as control. Ethanol extracts were prepared by following the procedure described in Chandramohan et al 1967. Total phenol in the ethanol extract was estimated using Folin-ciocalteu reagent.

TNAU7124 contained more total phe, no1 than ASD5, CO 40, and TN1 (Table 1). The percentage changes in total phenol in inoculated plants compared with uninoculated plants are presented in Table 2.

Total phenolic content of the four varieties increased. but not uniformly, with inoculation. It decreased with plant age. The interactions between variety and crop stage, variety and sampling time, variety and treatment were highly significant.

Ortho-dihydroxy level increased 7 DI in TNAU7124, ASD5, and CO 40. Tillering and boot leaf stage inoculation

Table 2. Percentage changes in total phenolics and ortho-dihydroxy phenol in rice varieties due to *X. oryzae* infection. ^a

Variety	Plant stage ^b	Changes (%) in content of					
		Phenol			Ortho-dihydroxy phenol		
		7 DI	10 DI	15 DI	7 DI	10 DI	15 DI
TNAU7124	S	+23.60	+13.15	+ 4.38	+12.12	+17.80	- 4.55
	T	+ 9.87	+10.78	+10.87	+68.75	+73.58	+16.27
	B	+15.54	+12.61	+16.26	+97.30	+ 1.39	+30.43
ASD5	S	+11.11	+23.45	+ 8.22	+15.71	-16.27	- 0.48
	T	+ 1.20	+ 3.59	- 1.38	+67.80	+30.26	+16.91
	B	+ 0.76	- 0.81	- 21.37	+22.46	+44.44	+16.48
TN1	S	+ 3.16	+17.06	+12.32	-20.00	+15.48	+14.69
	T	-15.45	-14.78	+ 8.53	+11.16	+12.70	+35.65
	B	+ 2.44	+ 7.84	- 5.56	- 2.60	+21.67	+60.66
CO 40	S	+ 7.96	- 6.71	-10.04	+25.87	+ 3.27	+ 3.27
	T	+ 8.23	+ 4.42	1.55	+19.40	+ 2.04	+56.70
	B	+ 1.31	+ 5.13	+ 6.67	+ 2.67	+ 0.98	-37.76

^a DI = days after inoculation. ^b S = seedling, T = tillering, B = boot leaf.

of TNAU7124 also caused accumulation of ortho-dihydroxy phenol. During last sampling ortho-dihydroxy phenol decreased except in TN1. Interactions be-

tween variety and stage, variety and sampling time, stage and sampling time, variety and treatment, and stage and treatment were significantly superior. □

Pest management and control INSECTS

Fungal pathogens of *Nephotettix virescens* Dist. and *Nilaparvata lugens* Stål

M. Balasubramanian and V. Mariappan, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore, India

The potential benefits of biological insect pest control methods, especially those using bacteria and viruses, are well known. Fungi are now explored as a control method for certain insects, including green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* and brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens*.

GLH and BPH were found dead in unsprayed standing rice crops during cold months. Specimens from 26 locations in Tamil Nadu and Kerala States, India, were collected and examined.

Dead insects showed mummification, changes in morphological characters, and outgrowth of fungal tissues. Specimens were washed in three changes of sterile water and plated in sterile agar medium

to isolate microorganisms. Nine species of fungi were isolated from GLH and six from BPH. Five species of fungi were common to both insect species (see table).

Pathogenicity tests showed that *Fusarium* sp., isolated from GLH, and *Cephalosporium* sp., isolated from BPH, caused infection and death of both insects 4-7 days after treatment. *Fusarium* sp. caused 72.4 and 48.3% mortality of GLH nymphs and adults and 67.3 and 40.0% mortality of BPH nymphs and adults. *Cephalosporium* sp. caused GLH mortality rate of 70.7 and 37.5% and killed 75.9 and 52.7%

Fungi isolated from *N. virescens* and *N. lugens*.

Species	Common to both
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	*
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	*
<i>Mucor</i> sp.	*
<i>Phoma</i> sp.	*
<i>Rhizopus</i> sp.	*
<i>Penicillium</i> sp.	
<i>Alternaria tenuis</i>	
<i>Curvularia</i> sp.	
<i>Fusarium oxysporium</i>	
<i>Cephalosporium lecanii</i>	

BPH nymphs and adults. Spraying fungal suspension containing conidia and mycelia caused higher death rates than spraying the culture filtrate or treating the insects with fungal mass.

The International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) invites all scientists to contribute concise summaries of significant rice research for publication. Contributions should be limited to one or two pages and no more than two short tables, figures, or photographs. Contributions are subject to editing and abridgement to meet space limitations. Authors will be identified by name, title, and research organization.

The two fungal species do not harm rice, cotton, brinjal, tomato, and sorghum. Identification of the *Fusarium* sp. as

Fusarium oxysporium Schlecht (Booth 1971) was confirmed by Commonwealth Mycological Institute, England. The *Cepha-*

losporium sp. was identified as *Cephalosporium lecanii* Zimm (Subramaniam 1971). □

Effect of simulated rainfall on insecticide spray effectiveness

N. V. Krishnaiah and M. B. Kalode, All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 500 030, A.P., India

During wet season, rainfall causes insecticide sprays to lose effectiveness and spraying often must be repeated. A greenhouse experiment used simulated rainfall and insecticides recommended to control green leafhopper (GLH) and brown planthopper (BPH) to determine the time lapse between insecticide application and rainfall that does not reduce insecticide effectiveness. Carbaryl and monocrotophos (0.05%) were sprayed on 45-day-old TN1 plants with a fine atomizer until runoff.

Effect of simulated rainfall on effectiveness of insecticide sprays.

Insecticide	Time lapse (h) between spray and rainfall	Mortality (%) at days after spraying		
		GLH		BPH
		3d	8d	3d
Carbaryl (50 WP)	0.5	43	17	10
	3	40	27	43
	24	100	57	87
	No rainfall	100	97	100
Monocrotophos (40 EC)	0.5	77	70	3
	3	83	60	10
	24	97	87	30
	No rainfall	100	100	80
Untreated control		3	0	0

Plants were subjected to about 2 cm simulated rainfall from a sprinkler can fixed 183 cm above the plants 0.5, 3, and 24 h after treatment. Effectiveness was tested by caging GLH adults and BPH nymphs on the plants for 48 h.

Insecticide effectiveness was substantially reduced by rainfall 3 h after spraying (see table). Effect of rainfall after 24 h was small except on monocrotophos used against BPH. □

Incidence of rice gall midge at Bhubaneswar, Orissa, India

B. C. Jena, N. C. Patnaik, Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology, Bhubaneswar; and N. Panda, Entomology Department, IRR I

Rainfall and relative humidity govern the activity of rice gall midge (GM) *Orseolia oryzae* in rice fields and degree of infestation is higher in the wet season than in the dry.

To study the fluctuations of GM attack, susceptible Jaya variety was transplanted in 8-m² plots at 2-week intervals beginning Jan 1977 and ending Dec 1981.

Plantings were replicated 3 times and silvershoot count, total plant population basis, was recorded 60 days after transplanting (DT) in a sample of 240 hills/plot.

GM infestation (see figure) was highest (17%) in Oct, corresponding to Aug planting, which is common among farmers in this rainfed area. Low rainfall months had silvershoot levels below 4%

GM infestation had a positive, significant correlation ($n = 72$) with the amount of rainfall received during the preceding 15 days ($r = 0.446$) and 30 days ($r = 0.640$), indicating the lag effect of rainfall on GM activity. Relative humidity had no lag effect ($r = 0.683$). □

Evaluation of some wild *Oryza* species as yellow rice borer hosts

S. M. Zaheruddeen and P. S. Prakasa Rao, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack 753 006, India

Yellow rice borer *Scirpophaga incertulas* is regarded as monophagous with exclusive host specificity to rice. African rice *Oryza glaberrima* and 16 wild rice species were compared with established host variety *O. sativa* (cultivar Jaya) to determine other potential hosts (see table).

Newly hatched borer larvae were reared on cut stem pieces until pupation. They were also released on whole plants growing in earthen pots which were observed for damage symptoms and adult emergence.

All larvae placed on *O. perrieri* stem pieces died by the fifth day. Larvae pupated on *O. rufipogon*, *O. nivara*, *O. glaberrima*, and *O. latifolia*, as on *O. sativa*. Larvae survived and grew for more than 10 days on the other species but died without pupating.

No visual borer damage appeared for 10 days on 6 species of whole plants and

Gall midge incidence at 60 days after transplanting (DT) in a fortnightly planted Jaya crop.